

1 Application of catalytic hydrodechlorination for
2 the fast removal of chlorinated azole
3 pesticides in drinking water

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11 Graphical abstract

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25 **Abstract**

26 Catalytic hydrodechlorination (HDC) is regarded as a promising purifying technology for
27 drinking water treatment. So far, it has proved to be highly effective for the removal of
28 different groups of chlorinated micropollutants including pharmaceuticals, neonicotinoid
29 pesticides, personal care products or chloroacetic acids. The azole pesticides, recently
30 included in the EU Watch Lists (Decisions 2020/1161 and 2022/1307), are a group of
31 micropollutants of particular concern for drinking water given their high toxicity,
32 persistence, and bioaccumulation potential. In this work, the feasibility of HDC for the
33 removal of a representative group of chlorinated azole pesticides tebuconazole (TEB),
34 tetraconazole (TET), prochloraz (PCZ), penconazole (PEN), metconazole (MET) and
35 imazalil (IMZ)) is demonstrated, and their reactivity is compared with that observed for
36 other halogenated micropollutant groups. Notably, all the pesticides investigated in this
37 work ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) were completely dechlorinated within 30 min under ambient conditions
38 using a 1 wt. % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst concentration of 0.25 g L^{-1} and a H₂ feeding of 50 mL
39 N min^{-1} . The experimental data were accurately described by a pseudo-first order kinetic
40 equation and rate constant values in the range from 1.08 to $2.60 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ were
41 obtained. These values are quite close to those achieved for the most reactive
42 neonicotinoid pesticides and significantly higher than the obtained for chloroacetic acids
43 and most pharmaceuticals (e.g. diclofenac, sertraline or chlorpromazine). From the
44 identification of the generated reaction intermediates and the final non-chlorinated
45 products, sequential reaction pathways were proposed for each pollutant. Remarkably,
46 despite the high toxicity exhibited by the azole pesticides tested, with LC₅₀ values within
47 the $0.4 - 7.0 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ range using *A. salina*, HDC effluents were non-toxic in all cases.
48 Furthermore, the catalyst showed a remarkable stability upon three consecutive runs.
49 Finally, the versatility of the process was demonstrated in the treatment of real aqueous
50 matrices such as DWTP and tap water, where no significant differences were found either
51 in terms of activity or stability.

52

53 **Keywords**

54 Catalytic hydrodechlorination; Azole compounds; EU Watch List; Water treatment;
55 Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst.

56 **1. Introduction**

57 The access to safe and clean drinking water is crucial for human health and thus,
58 it is considered a basic human right. Drinking water treatment plants (DWTPs) are the
59 responsible for guaranteeing that potable water quality fulfills the requirements
60 established in the regulation. Accordingly, these treatment plants are designed for the
61 removal of microorganisms, turbidity, and natural organic matter, paying special attention
62 to the general appearance, odor and taste of water. Nevertheless, the fresh waters
63 employed by DWTPs generally contain a wide range of micropollutants that so far have
64 not been considered in the regulation. A particularly relevant example is the occurrence
65 of pesticides, widely employed in agriculture to enhance food production by preventing
66 or eliminating pests, weeds and fungal diseases (Aktar et al., 2009). Among pesticides,
67 fungicides play an essential role in modern agriculture, representing over 35% of the
68 global pesticide market share, which is expected to increase due to population growth and
69 increasing fungal resistance (Zubrod et al., 2019). Furthermore, fungicides are also
70 widely used in urban landscapes, building boards and paints (Liu et al., 2021a). Azole
71 compounds represent one of the most employed fungicides nowadays (Jørgensen and
72 Heick, 2021). Apart from their desired antifungal properties, these compounds are
73 characterized by high a persistence and remarkable toxicity, representing a high risk for
74 both the environment and public health. Residual azole fungicides in the aquatic
75 environment could cause adverse effects on different levels of organisms such as toxic
76 effects on algal growth as well as endocrine disruption in fish (Chen and Ying, 2015). For
77 these reasons, a representative group of azole pesticides have been included in the most
78 recent Watch Lists approved by the EU (Decisions 2020/1161 and 2022/1307). Azole
79 pesticides may reach the aquatic environment mainly by surface run-off, spray drift and
80 soil seepage (Kahle et al., 2008). Therefore, they are practically ubiquitous in water

81 bodies, being tebuconazole (TEB) the most frequently detected fungicide in surface
82 waters worldwide (de Souza et al., 2020).

83 DWTPs are not specifically designed for the removal of micropollutants, and they
84 are particularly ineffective for azole compounds elimination (Assress et al., 2020). In fact,
85 these compounds or their metabolites have been commonly detected both in the
86 catchment water, treated water, and tap water samples (Liu et al., 2021b). High detection
87 frequencies of azole pesticides in catchment waters have been reported by several authors
88 (Dong et al., 2021; Elfikrie et al., 2020a), and most of them are inadequately removed
89 after the conventional drinking water treatment processes. For instance, the detected
90 concentration of TEB in raw water samples ranged from 5 to 510 ng L⁻¹. Accordingly,
91 the development of advanced water treatments to warrant the complete removal of such
92 persistent species is crucial. Adsorption of azole pesticides onto activated carbon has
93 proved to be quite effective in the removal of these pollutants (Ha et al., 2020).
94 Nevertheless, this is a non-destructive process, which requires further management of the
95 saturated adsorbent. Advanced oxidation processes, in particular Fenton and photo-
96 Fenton, have been also explored for the elimination of several azole pesticides like
97 imazalil and TEB with mineralization yields between 75% and 85% in the Fenton and
98 photo Fenton processes, respectively (Carlos Silva Costa Teixeira et al., 2005; Santiago
99 et al., 2018). However, the possible formation of reaction intermediates even more toxic
100 than the parent compounds clearly limits its implementation for drinking water treatment
101 (Babuponnusami and Muthukumar, 2014; Bautista et al., 2008).

102 In recent contributions, the effectiveness of catalytic hydrodechlorination (HDC)
103 for the removal of different chlorinated micropollutant groups like pharmaceuticals,
104 personal care products, neonicotinoid pesticides or haloacetic acids was demonstrated
105 (Nieto-Sandoval et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2015). Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge,

106 HDC was not explored so far for the elimination of azole compounds. Since the number
107 and nature of halogenated substituents in the structure of the micropollutants influences
108 its reactivity, as well as the different heteroatoms and functional groups contained in the
109 parent molecule, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the HDC process for these
110 pollutants is of great interest. Upon HDC, organochlorinated compounds react with
111 hydrogen in presence of a solid catalyst, resulting in the formation of chlorine-free
112 products and the release of hydrochloric acid (Ardila et al., 2007) . This transformation
113 usually leads to a significant reduction of the ecotoxicity of the effluent. Furthermore,
114 HDC reactions can be carried out under ambient operating conditions, being also effective
115 for the treatment of wide range of initial pollutant concentrations.

116 This work aims to evaluate the feasibility of HDC for the removal of a
117 representative group of chlorinated azole pesticides included in the last EU Watch Lists:
118 prochloraz (PCZ), tebuconazole (TEB), tetraconazole (TET), imazalil (IMZ),
119 metconazole (MET) and penconazole (PEN). A commercial Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst was used
120 given its prominent role in this field (Mackenzie et al., 2006). The kinetics of the HDC
121 reactions was investigated and reaction pathways were accordingly proposed.
122 Furthermore, the treatment of azole pesticides mixtures was also studied, and the
123 reactivity of this group of micropollutants towards HDC was compared with that showed
124 by other families like neonicotinoid pesticides, pharmaceuticals, personal care products
125 and chloroacetic acids. The effectiveness of the treatment was further demonstrated by
126 evaluating the ecotoxicity breakdown of the effluents. Furthermore, the stability of the
127 catalyst was proved in three consecutive runs and the versatility of the process was
128 demonstrated in real aqueous matrices.

129 **2. Materials and methods**

130 *2.1 Materials*

131 The azole pesticides ($\geq 98\%$) tested in this work were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich.
 132 **Table 1** collects their main properties. Sodium carbonate (99.8%) and sodium
 133 bicarbonate (99.9%) were provided by PanReac and Sigma-Aldrich, respectively.
 134 Acetonitrile (99.9%) and hydrogen (99.999%) were delivered by Fisher Scientific and
 135 Praxair, respectively. The powdered ($\sim 24 \mu\text{m}$) Pd/Al₂O₃ (1% wt.) catalyst was supplied
 136 by Alfa Aesar. This catalyst was fully characterized elsewhere (Nieto-Sandoval et al.,
 137 2022, 2018). Briefly, the Pd content was 0.95% wt., the Pd nanoparticles showed a mean
 138 particle diameter of 3.3 nm, the specific surface area was 147 m² g⁻¹ and the pH_{PZC} value
 139 was close to 7.6. Regarding the oxidation state of Pd, a molar Pd⁰ /Pdⁿ⁺ molar ratio of
 140 1.04 was determined. Unless otherwise indicated, deionized water was used as reaction
 141 matrix.

142 **Table 1.** Main properties of the chlorinated azole pesticides tested in this work.

Compound	Abbreviation	Structure	pKa	Molecular weight (g mol ⁻¹)
Prochloraz	PCZ		3.8 (Stutz and Malissa, 1998)	376.6
Tebuconazole	TEB		5.0 (Čadková et al., 2013)	307.8
Metconazole	MET		11.3 (Lee et al., 2019)	319.8
Penconazole	PEN		5.2 (Čadková et al., 2013)	284.2
Imazalil	IMZ		6.5 (Holmes and Eckert, 1999)	297.2

Tetraconazole

TET

0.6 (Lee et al., 2019)

372.1

143

144 *2.2 Experimental procedure*

145 HDC runs were carried out in a batch-wise slurry-type reactor (450 mL) under
146 ambient conditions (1 atm and 25 °C) and neutral pH at 900 rpm stirring rate (to avoid
147 external mass transfer limitations) (Nieto-Sandoval et al., 2018). The initial pesticides
148 concentration was established at 100 µg L⁻¹, although it was raised up to 10 mg L⁻¹ in a
149 particular set of experiments to allow the identification of the reaction intermediates and
150 final products. The catalyst concentration and H₂ feed were set at 0.25 g L⁻¹ and 50 N mL
151 min⁻¹, respectively. The hydrogen was bubbled from the bottom of the reactor using a
152 diffuser to achieve small diameter bubbles and high gas to liquid transfer surface. Blank
153 experiments were performed in the absence of H₂ to discriminate the role of adsorption
154 along the HDC process. All experiments were carried out in triplicate, being the standard
155 deviation below 5%.

156 *2.3 Analytical methods*

157 The evolution of HDC reactions was followed by analyzing the samples
158 periodically withdrawn from the reactor. Prior analysis, samples were centrifuged to
159 separate the solid catalyst. The target pollutants, intermediates and products were
160 measured by an HPLC-UV (Shimadzu, model Prominence-i, LC2030C LT) using an
161 Agilent Eclipse Plus C₁₈ column (15 cm length, 4.6 mm diameter) as stationary phase.
162 Mixtures of acetonitrile and deionized water at different volume ratios (55/45% for TET,
163 60/40% for PEN, PCZ and TEB and 65/35% for IMZ and MET) were used as mobile
164 phases. Quantification was carried out at 195 nm for IMZ, 210 nm for TET, 212 nm for

165 PCZ and PEN, 222 nm for MET and at 223 nm for TEB. The chloride ions released along
166 the HDC reaction were quantified by ion chromatography (Metrohm 883 IC Plus). A
167 Metrosep A supp 5-250 column (25 cm length, 4 mm internal diameter) was used as
168 stationary phase and an aqueous solution of Na₂CO₃ (3.2 mM) and NaHCO₃ (1 mM) as
169 mobile phase. Elemental analyses of fresh and used catalysts were carried out on a LECO
170 CHNS-932 Elemental Analyzer.

171 2.4 Ecotoxicity tests

172 *Artemia salina* was used as a representative organism to assess the toxicity of both
173 the target pollutants and HDC effluents. The procedure followed was reported in a
174 previous work (Munoz et al., 2019). *Artemia salina* cysts (0.5 g) were incubated in an
175 aquarium containing 0.47 L synthetic seawater at 30°C, illuminated and under continuous
176 aeration. Cysts hatched at around 24 h of incubation. Synthetic seawater consisted of 15
177 g synthetic sea salt (Aquaforest) dissolved in 0.47 L deionized water. The standard
178 conditions used to evaluate the toxicity were: 30°C, 35 g L⁻¹ synthetic sea salt, neutral pH
179 and darkness. Five concentrations of each pesticide were tested. Three control replicates
180 were also performed in the seawater medium alone. Each vial contained 20 organisms in
181 2 mL of sample and was placed in an incubator for a period of 72 h. Afterwards, nauplii
182 were observed and dead nauplii were counted. Nauplii were considered dead if no
183 movement was detected during 10 s of observation. The lethal concentration (LC₅₀),
184 defined as the concentration of the contaminant that kills 50% of the nauplii in 72 h
185 (Munoz et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2017), was used to determine the toxicity of the pesticides.
186 Moreover, the HDC effluent samples were also evaluated, expressing the results in terms
187 of mortality (percentage of dead nauplii after incubation).

188 3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Catalytic hydrodechlorination of chlorinated azole pesticides

Figure 1 shows the evolution of the isolated azole pesticides ($100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) upon HDC using 0.25 g L^{-1} Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst under ambient conditions. As can be seen, all pollutants were completely degraded within 15 min reaction time, although slight variations in their disappearance rates were observed. The experimental data were successfully described by a pseudo-first order kinetic equation, obtaining the following rate constant values (correlation coefficients (r^2) between 0.95 and 1 were obtained in all cases): $2.60 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (TEB), $2.28 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (TET), $1.72 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (PEN and PCZ), $1.56 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (IMZ) and $1.08 \text{ L g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$ (MET). Accordingly, the pesticides reactivity towards HDC decreased following the order: TEB>TET>PEN~PCZ>IMZ>MET. The electrostatic interaction between the target pollutants and the catalyst surface seems to play a non-despicable role on the reactivity trend observed. Except for TEB, an almost linear correlation between the rate constant value and the pKa value of the azole pesticide was found (**Figure 2**). It must be noted that, under the operating conditions tested, the catalyst surface was positively charged ($\text{pH}_{\text{PZC}} = 7.6$). MET, which showed the lowest HDC rate constant, was the only compound that suffered electrostatic repulsion from the catalyst surface as it was positively charged at neutral pH ($\text{pKa} = 11.6$). The rest of azole pesticides were negatively charged and thus, their interaction with the catalyst surface was favored. In fact, the rate constant value increased with decreasing the pKa value of the target pollutant, with the exception of TEB. This azole pesticide showed the highest rate constant value among the ones tested, which could be due to the fact that it only contains one chlorine substituent in its structure while the other azole pesticides show two or three substituents. Furthermore, it also contains a hydroxyl substituent, which could also enhance the HDC rate (Shin and Keane, 1998). In **Figure 2**, despite its lower pKa, PCZ, with three chlorine substituents, showed a rate

214 constant value exactly the same as PEN, with only two chlorine substituents, which
215 further demonstrates that the reactivity of azole pesticides decreases with increasing the
216 number of chlorine substituents. These results are consistent with the fact that TET, PEN
217 and IMZ, all with two chlorine substituents, followed a clear linear trend between their
218 pKa and rate constant values.

219

220 **Fig. 1.** Evolution of the isolated azole pesticides upon HDC reaction ($[\text{Pesticide}]_0 = 100$
221 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $H_2 = 50 \text{ N mL min}^{-1}$; $[\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3] = 0.25 \text{ g L}^{-1}$; $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Experimental (symbols)
222 and model fit (solid lines)

223

224

225 **Fig. 2.** Relationship between the HDC rate constant values at 25 °C and the pKa of
 226 azole pesticides.

227

228 An additional set of experiments was carried out increasing the initial
 229 concentration of the azole pesticides up to 10 mg L⁻¹ to get better insights on the reaction
 230 intermediates and products generated during the HDC process (see Fig. S1 of the
 231 Supplementary Material for experimental data). Adsorption experiments were also
 232 carried out with each of the pesticides (see Fig. S2 of the Supplementary Material for
 233 experimental data). Another experiment was carried out in the absence of the catalyst for
 234 the removal of the azole pesticides. As shown in the fig S3 of the Supplementary Material,
 235 as expected, none of the pesticides were removed in the presence of H₂ (<5%). The
 236 analysis of the samples along reaction time by HPLC-UV allowed to determine the
 237 chemical structures of those species. The chloride ions released along the HDC reaction
 238 were quantified by ion chromatography. Accordingly, reaction pathways were proposed
 239 for the different azole compounds tested (**Scheme 1**). It must be highlighted that,
 240 regardless of the chemical structure of the parent compound, complete
 241 hydrodechlorination of the azole pesticides was achieved at the end of the reactions. A

242 consecutive reaction pathway was proposed in all cases, which implies the sequential
243 removal of all the chlorine atoms from the parent compound obtaining as final products
244 non-chlorinated species without further hydrogenation. The evolution of the species along
245 reaction is collected in Fig. S4-S9 of the Supplementary Material. It must be noted that
246 TET, which apart from chlorine contains four fluorine substituents, did not suffer its
247 complete hydrodehalogenation as fluorine substituents were not removed. This fact could
248 be attributed to the higher C-F binding energy (485 kJ mol^{-1}) in comparison with the
249 chlorine binding energy (339 kJ mol^{-1}) (Sorrilha et al., 2004). An additional experiment
250 performed at relatively high temperature ($55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) allowed to confirm this hypothesis since
251 an increase of the reaction temperature allows to obtain not only the complete
252 hydrodechlorination of TET, but also its partial hydrodefluorination (**Figure 3**).

253

254 **Fig. 3.** Evolution of TET and fluoride upon HDH reaction ($[\text{TET}]_0 = 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$; $\text{H}_2 =$
255 50 N mL min^{-1} ; $[\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3] = 0.25 \text{ g L}^{-1}$; $55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

256

257

259 3.2 Ecotoxicity tests

260 The ecotoxicity of the azole pesticides and the final HDC effluents was analyzed using
261 the brine shrimp *Artemia salina* lethality bioassay. *Artemia salina* is recognized as an
262 outstanding target organism for ecotoxicity testing given its high filtration rate which
263 makes it highly sensitive to the presence of xenobiotics (Rajabi et al., 2015). **Table 3**
264 collects the ecotoxicity values of the azole pesticide tested in this work expressed as
265 lethal concentration (LC_{50} ($mg L^{-1}$)) at 72 h exposure time. As can be observed, the lowest
266 value of LC_{50} ($0.4 mg L^{-1}$) was obtained for IMZ, which indicates that this azole
267 compound is the most toxic among the pesticides evaluated in this study. The higher
268 lethality of IMZ can be related to its chemical structure which contains a chiral center that
269 gives rise to two enantiomers, which, while sharing physical and chemical properties,
270 have different biological effects (Li et al., 2019). These results are in agreement with
271 some studies evaluating the LC_{50} of IMZ and PEN in trout where the resulting LC_{50} value
272 for IMZ was $1.1 mg L^{-1}$ (Michael A. Kamrin, 1999; Yoloğlu, 2019). All in all, all the
273 azole pesticides tested showed a remarkable ecotoxicity (being the highest LC_{50} value of
274 $7 mg L^{-1}$) and thus, their effective elimination from water is crucial.

275 The ecotoxicity of the HDC effluents against *Artemia salina* nauplii was also
276 evaluated with a set of experiments with an initial concentration of $10 mg L^{-1}$. In all cases,
277 the ecotoxicity significantly decreased after the treatment achieving values of elimination
278 between approximately 20 to 90% (data in Table S1 of the Supplementary Material).
279 This is consistent with the transformation of the organochlorine pollutants during the
280 HDC reactions giving rise to chlorine-free products which usually are more
281 biodegradable and, therefore, easier to be removed in the aquatic environment.

282 To further demonstrate the effectiveness of HDC in reducing the ecotoxicity of
283 pesticides, another set of experiments were carried out with all contaminants with an

284 initial concentration of 3 mg L⁻¹. In this case, a significant decrease in mortality was
 285 obtained after HDC treatment regardless the pesticides (see results in **Table 2**). Notably,
 286 the ecotoxicity abatement in the case of TEB was complete, which allows to confirm that
 287 chlorine substituents are the mainly responsible for the ecotoxicity of azole pesticides.

288 **Table 2.** LC₅₀ values and mortality of the six azole pesticides tested in this work.

Pesticide	LC ₅₀ (mg L ⁻¹)		Mortality (%)	
	72 h	Initial Solution	HDC effluent	Mortality reduction
TEB	2.5	26.4	< 0.1	>99.9
PEN	1.3	58.8	41.1	30.1
TET	3.4	26.4	8.8	66.6
MET	7.0	24.9	5.8	76.7
IMZ	0.4	58.8	32.3	45
PCZ	3.4	50.0	14.7	70.6

289 *3.3 HDC of azole pesticides mixture*

290 Azole pesticides do not appear isolated in real aqueous matrices. For instance, in
 291 2011, different pesticide residues were detected in water samples from the Ebro River
 292 (Spain), being IMZ and PCZ two of the most frequent azole compounds identified (70%
 293 of the samples) (Ccanccapa et al., 2016). Several azole compounds such as TEB and
 294 propiconazole have been also detected in water samples collected at the intake point of
 295 DWTP (Elfikrie et al. 2020).

296 To evaluate possible competing effects between the target pollutants upon HDC, the
 297 treatment of a pesticide mixture was accomplished. The experiments were performed with
 298 an initial concentration of each pesticide of 100 µg L⁻¹ while the catalyst concentration
 299 was established at 0.25 g L⁻¹. As can be seen in **Figure 4**, all pollutants were removed in
 300 a relatively short reaction time (< 30 min), although it was somehow longer than the
 301 observed with the isolated pesticides (< 15 min). Nevertheless, it must be noted that the
 302 same catalyst concentration (and H₂ feed) was employed to degrade the whole pollutants

303 mixture. As for the results obtained in the treatment of the isolated pesticides, the pseudo-
304 first order kinetic constants were obtained for the HDC of each azole compound when
305 they were treated in mixture (correlation coefficients were above 0.95 in all cases (see
306 Table S2 of Supplementary Material). Competitive effects can explain the differences
307 found in the reactivity trend observed between the treatment of isolated pesticides and the
308 complex mixture. Again, the interaction of the pollutants with the catalyst surface due to
309 electrostatic attraction/repulsion as well as the number of chlorine substituents present in
310 the molecule are the main factors that explain the reactivity trend observed. In this sense,
311 MET, whose interaction with the catalyst surface is not favored due to electrostatic
312 repulsion, showed again the lowest rate constant value. PEN, TET and IMZ, whose
313 interaction with the catalyst surface is favored according to their pKa values and with two
314 chlorine substituents in their structures, presented very similar rate constant values. On
315 the other hand, in contrast to the behavior observed in the treatment of isolated pesticides,
316 PCZ exhibited the highest rate constant value, possibly due to the fact that it contains
317 three chlorine substituents in its structure. Although the presence of such amount of
318 chlorine substituents could somehow decrease the HDC rate, its interaction with the Pd
319 nanoparticles present on the catalyst surface is significantly favored and thus, it is
320 preferentially adsorbed in comparison with the other azole pesticides present in the
321 mixture. This is consistent with previous works of the literature where it was
322 demonstrated that highly chlorinated species are more strongly adsorbed on Pd catalysts
323 (Murena and Schioppa, 2000).

324

325 **Fig. 4.** HDC of azole pesticide mixture ($[\text{Pesticide}]_0 = 100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $H_2 = 50 \text{ N mL min}^{-1}$;
 326 $[\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3] = 0.25\text{g L}^{-1}$; $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Experimental (symbols) and model fit (solid lines).

327

328 3.4 Stability tests

329 Catalyst deactivation represents one of the main limitations of HDC technology given the
 330 high costs of the catalysts involved. The main reasons behind this phenomenon are mainly
 331 the poisoning of Pd active centers by their interaction with the HCl released along reaction
 332 as well as the fouling (and even pore blocking) promoted by the adsorption of organic
 333 compounds onto the catalyst surface (Ordóñez et al., 2007; Yuan and Keane, 2003). In
 334 this work, the stability of the Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst was evaluated in three consecutive HDC
 335 runs with each (isolated) azole pesticide. **Figure 5** collects the pseudo-first rate constant
 336 values obtained in the three consecutive runs. Notably, the catalyst showed a remarkable
 337 stability and no signs of deactivation were found in any case. It must be noted that, after
 338 three consecutive HDC runs, the catalyst maintained its properties practically unchanged,
 339 and palladium leaching was negligible (<0.1% wt.). In the same line, elemental analyses
 340 of the used catalyst revealed a negligible content of carbon on the catalyst surface after
 341 reaction, which allowed to discard the blocking of the Pd active centers by organic
 342 molecules along reaction (see Table S3 of Supplementary Material). These results are in

343 good agreement with those reported in the literature using Pd/Al₂O₃ catalysts for the
344 removal of other chlorinated micropollutants by HDC under similar conditions (Nieto-
345 Sandoval et al., 2020b) and confirm that Pd/Al₂O₃ is a resistant catalyst for HDC
346 reactions. In all cases, the lower decomposition rate observed in the first HDC run can be
347 related to the initial adsorption step required for beginning the reaction. However, in the
348 second and third reaction runs, organic species are adsorbed on the catalyst surface at the
349 beginning of the run, so this stage did not slow down the initial reaction rate (Nieto-
350 Sandoval et al., 2018).

351

352 **Fig. 5.** Rate constant values obtained in the HDC of the isolated azole pesticides upon
353 three consecutive HDC runs. ([Pesticide]₀ = 100 µg L⁻¹ ; H₂ = 50 N mL min⁻¹ ;
354 [Pd/Al₂O₃] = 0.25 g L⁻¹ ; 25 °C)

355

356 3.5 Catalytic hydrodechlorination in real aqueous matrices

357 To further demonstrate the feasibility of HDC for the removal of azole pesticides in
358 drinking water, the effectiveness of the process was also evaluated using different real
359 water samples as reaction matrices. In particular, tap water and surface water were tested.
360 This series of experiments was carried out with the pesticide mixture. The main properties
361 of the real aqueous matrices are summarized in **Table 3**. Briefly, the conductivity value
362 of tap water is twice that of surface water. The concentration of chlorides, species which

363 can act as poison for the Pd active centers of the catalyst, was 12.1 and 14.5 mg L⁻¹ for
 364 tap and surface water, respectively. The total organic carbon content was quite similar for
 365 the two samples (2.8 mg L⁻¹ and 2.2 mg L⁻¹ for the tap and surface water, respectively).
 366 Moreover, tap water shows a somewhat higher pH which is consistent with its higher
 367 carbonate content (measured as inorganic carbon (IC) concentration).

368 **Table 3.** Main characteristics of the real aqueous matrices

Parameter	Deionized water	Tap water	Surface water
pH	6.9	8	6.8
TOC (mg L ⁻¹)	0.54	2.8	2.2
IC (mg L ⁻¹)	0.11	4.3	1.6
Conductivity (μS cm ⁻¹)	0.05	80.7	48.9
Cl ⁻ (mg L ⁻¹)	0.09	12.1	14.5

369

370 The evolution of the azole pesticides along the HDC reactions in the different
 371 reaction matrices is shown in Figure 6. As can be seen, complete degradation of the
 372 pesticides was achieved in all cases regardless of the reaction aqueous matrices, which
 373 demonstrates the versatility of the system. In fact, the rate constant values obtained were
 374 quite similar to the achieved in deionized water. Accordingly, the low carbon content as
 375 well as the presence of co-existing species in these water matrices do not seem to hinder
 376 the activity of the catalytic system (see Table 3). As can be shown, the activity decreased
 377 in tap water and surface water (see Table 4) could be mainly attributed to the higher
 378 conductivity, and therefore, higher ions concentration, since they can compete for Pd
 379 catalytic centers. Yuan & Keane, (2004), studied the hydrodechlorination (HDC) of 2,4-
 380 dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP) and 2-chlorophenol (2-CP) on 1% Pd/C and Pd/Al₂O₃ under
 381 minimal mass transport conditions. The HDC of 2,4-DCP generated HCl and 2-CP as a
 382 partially dechlorinated intermediate, which was further hydrodechlorinated to
 383 cyclohexanone. According to this work, inhibitory effects due to the presence of HCl

384 were observed on the activity of the catalyst during the HDC reaction, while the
 385 selectivity towards the reaction products was maintaining unchanged.

386

387 **Fig. 6.** HDC of azole compounds mixture in tap water (A) and surface water (B)
 388 ($[\text{Pesticide}]_0 = 100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $H_{20} = 50 \text{ N mL min}^{-1}$; $[\text{Pd}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3] = 0.25 \text{ g L}^{-1}$; $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$)

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390

391 **Table 4.** Values of the rate constant in the HDC of the azole pesticides in different
 392 water matrices.

Pesticide	$k \text{ (L g min}^{-1}\text{)}$		
	Deionized water	Tap water	Surface water
TEB	2.6 ($r^2=0.95$)	0.76 ($r^2=0.98$)	0.96 ($r^2=0.99$)
PEN	1.72 ($r^2=0.97$)	0.72 ($r^2=0.99$)	0.88 ($r^2=0.98$)
TET	2.28 ($r^2=0.99$)	0.80 ($r^2=0.98$)	0.80 ($r^2=0.92$)
MET	1.08 ($r^2=0.97$)	0.88 ($r^2=0.99$)	0.88 ($r^2=0.99$)
IMZ	1.56 ($r^2=0.97$)	1.04 ($r^2=0.99$)	1.04 ($r^2=0.98$)
PCZ	1.72 ($r^2=0.99$)	1.08 ($r^2=0.99$)	1.08 ($r^2=0.98$)

393

394 3.6 HDC of azole pesticides in the context of EU Watch Lists Micropollutants

395 HDH is an efficient and versatile process, as it can be applied to different
 396 families of micropollutants included in the different EU Watch Lists such as
 397 pharmaceuticals, pesticides or personal hygiene products, among others, or even the
 398 haloacetic acids, recently included in the Directive 2020/2184 on the quality of water

399 intended for human consumption. Depending on the nature of the organohalogen
400 compounds, such as the type and number of halogen substituents, their reactivity to
401 the HDH process would be different. **Figure 7** compares the pseudo-first apparent
402 rate constant values obtained in the HDH of the halogenated azole pesticides with
403 those obtained in the HDH of different representative halogenated groups of
404 micropollutants (Nieto-Sandoval et al., 2022, 2020b, 2020a, 2019, 2018). It can be
405 seen that the azole pesticides are quite reactive towards HDC in comparison with
406 neonicotinoid pesticides, pharmaceuticals and haloacetic acids. TEB and TET are the
407 most reactive compounds in this group, while MET is the least reactive azole
408 pesticide. Nonetheless, the reactivity of MET is notably higher than that of other
409 halogenated micropollutants such as the haloacetic acid MCAA, the pharmaceuticals
410 SRT and CPZ or the trihalomethanes. All these low reactivity micropollutants,
411 specially MCAA, can be used as indicators of the effectiveness of the HDH treatment,
412 since their complete elimination guarantees that the rest of the halogenated
413 micropollutants have been effectively converted.

414 All in all, it must be highlighted that all the compounds included in **Figure 7**
415 were completely eliminated in short reaction times (most of them in about 30 minutes
416 of reaction time) with rate constants ranging from 0.12 to 2.6 L g_{cat}⁻¹ min⁻¹, so this
417 technology can be proposed as a viable alternative for the abatement of a wide variety
418 of halogenated micropollutants in DWTPs.

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420

421 **Fig. 7.** Pseudo-first order rate constant values obtained in the HDC of representative
422 groups of micropollutants included in the EU Watch Lists ($[Pollutant]_0 = 100 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$;
423 $[H_2]_0: 50 \text{ N mL min}^{-1}$; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25 - 1.0 \text{ g L}^{-1}$).

424

425 **4. Conclusions**

426 The feasibility of HDC for the removal of a representative group of chlorinated azole
427 pesticides recently included in the EU Watch List has been demonstrated. Notably,
428 complete degradation of all compounds was achieved in a short reaction time (<15 min)
429 operating under ambient conditions and neutral pH. This group of micropollutants was
430 quite reactive towards HDC in comparison with neonicotinoid pesticides,
431 pharmaceuticals and chloroacetic acids. Furthermore, azole pesticides were completely
432 dechlorinated along reaction, achieving in all cases chlorine-free reaction products. This
433 transformation allowed to dramatically reduce the ecotoxicity of the effluents despite the
434 high ecotoxic character of all pesticides. Notably, the catalyst was fairly stable upon three
435 consecutive HDC runs, maintaining its properties practically unchanged. The versatility
436 of the catalytic system was finally demonstrated in real aqueous matrices (DWTP and tap
437 water), where the effects of the presence of co-existing substances were practically
438 negligible.

439

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461 **Table and Figure captions**

462 **Fig. 1.** Evolution of the isolated azole pesticides upon HDC reaction ($[Azole\ compound]_o$
463 $= 100\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $H_2 = 50\ \text{N mL min}^{-1}$; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $25\ ^\circ\text{C}$). Experimental
464 (symbols) and model fit (solid lines)..... 11

465 **Fig. 2.** Relationship between the HDC rate constant values and the pKa of azole
466 pesticides. 12

467 **Fig. 3.** Evolution of TET and fluoride upon HDC reaction ($[TET]_o = 10\ \text{mg L}^{-1}$; $H_2 = 50$
468 N mL min^{-1} ; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $55\ ^\circ\text{C}$). 13

469 **Fig. 4.** HDC of azole pesticide mixture ($[Pesticides]_o = 100\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $[H_2]_o = 50\ \text{mL min}^{-1}$
470 $^{-1}$; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $pH_o = 7$). Experimental (symbols) and model fit (solid lines).
471 18

472 **Fig. 5.** Rate constant values obtained in the HDC of the isolated azole pesticides upon
473 three consecutive HDC runs. ($[Azole\ compound]_o = 100\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $H_2 = 50\ \text{N mL min}^{-1}$;
474 $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $pH_o = 7$)..... 19

475 **Fig. 6.** HDC of azole compounds in tap water (A) and surface water (B) ($[Azole$
476 $compound]_o = 100\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; $[H_2]_o = 50\ \text{mL min}^{-1}$; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $pH_o = 7$)..... 21

477 **Fig. 7.** Pseudo-first order rate constant values obtained in the HDC of representative
478 groups of micropollutants included in the EU Watch Lists ($[Pollutant]_o = 100\ \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$;
479 $[H_2]_o: 50\ \text{mL min}^{-1}$; $[Pd/Al_2O_3] = 0.25 - 1.0\ \text{g L}^{-1}$; $pH_o = 7$). 23

480

481 **Table 1.** Main properties of the chlorinated azole pesticides tested in this work. 7

482 **Table 2.** LC₅₀ values and mortality of the six azole pesticides tested in this work. 16

483 **Table 3.** Main characteristics of the real aqueous matrices 20

484 **Table 4.** Values of the rate constant in the HDC of the azole pesticides in different water
485 matrices..... 21

487 **6. References**

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